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ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNITY-BASED WASTE MANAGEMENT METHODS IN AKOKO SOUTH WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Inappropriate methods of solid waste management are becoming challenging environmental issues in Nigeria with particular reference to Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo State. The persistence of these problems has necessitated a shift toward a more sustainable and community-based approach by implementing reduces reuse and recycle of solid waste. This study appraised the nature of waste generated and method of waste disposal adopted in the study area with a view of providing community-based sustainable approach to solid waste management. This research adopted descriptive survey method. Systematic random sampling technique was used to sample 455 household head in the study area. The stated hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), while the research questions were addressed with the use of descriptive analysis of simple percentage. The study observed a statistically significance difference between type of waste generated and method of waste disposal system in Akoko South West. The study revealed that tin/can (29%), plastic bag/bottle (28%) and paper/carton (23%) were the main types of waste generated in the study area. It also identified four methods of waste disposal: open burning (70.1%), dumping of waste into the open-drainage during rainfall (18%), burying of waste (9%) and dumping of waste at the collection point (2.9%). It was generally observed that majority of residents in the study area lack relevant technical knowledge on recycling of solid management. The study therefore recommended a shift in local or traditional strategy towards a sustainable approach by embracing solid waste reduction, reuse and recycling, and government funding be forthcoming to make necessary infrastructure improvements.*

Keyword: Solid Waste, Sustainable Management, Community-Based

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management has become a major global environmental challenge as rapid urbanization and industrialization continue to reshape the modern world. The increasing concentration of populations in urban centers has led to a steady rise in waste generation, making its effective management critical to environmental sustainability, public health, and economic development (Awopetu, Coker, Awopetu, Awopetu, Booth, Fullen, & Tannahill, 2013). Solid waste management encompasses the control of waste generation,

storage, collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal in an environmentally sound and economically viable manner. Globally, countries such as the United States, China, and India have adopted integrated systems that combine landfill use, recycling, and waste-to-energy conversion. Technological innovations, including bioreactor landfills, are being employed to improve efficiency and minimize environmental degradation. Central to these global strategies is the principle of the “Three Rs” reduces, reuse, and recycle which emphasizes minimizing waste creation, promoting material reuse, and conserving

resources to achieve sustainable waste management.

At the international level, sustainable waste management is aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 12 on responsible consumption and production (Adeleke, Oluwatobi & Akinlabi, 2021).). This goal encourages nations to reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling, and reuse. For instance, the United States' Solid Waste Act of 1990 established clear targets for diverting municipal waste from landfills through recycling and reuse initiatives. Similarly, international cooperation has strengthened waste management capacities in developing countries through technical support, funding, and the exchange of knowledge and best practices. These global and international frameworks reflect a growing consensus on the need for integrated waste management to promote environmental sustainability and safeguard human health.

However, despite global progress, many developing nations continue to face significant challenges in managing solid waste effectively (Ale, 2014). In most African countries, waste management responsibilities rest with municipal authorities, yet inadequate infrastructure, limited financial resources, and weak institutional frameworks hinder effective service delivery. Landfilling and open dumping remain the dominant disposal methods. Studies reveal those cities such as Accra, Kinshasa, Lagos, and Ibadan face chronic waste accumulation, with large portions of their populations lacking access to regular waste collection services. This situation has resulted in indiscriminate dumping in open spaces, drains, and waterways, leading to serious health risks such as malaria, cholera, and diarrhea, and contributing to environmental degradation and flooding during heavy rains. Therefore, while

solid waste management has gained global recognition as a sustainability priority, local implementation remains a pressing concern. Strengthening local systems through the adoption of the "Three Rs" approach reducing, reusing, and recycling alongside effective policy enforcement, public education, and community participation, can enhance environmental health and urban livability. Solid waste management thus stands as a vital component in achieving sustainable development, bridging the gap between global environmental goals and local urban realities.

Solid waste generation and management remain major environmental challenges in most developing urban areas, and Akoko South West is not exempted. The processes of waste generation, storage, collection, transportation, and disposal are inadequately managed, resulting in unhygienic and unsafe environmental conditions. Large volumes of uncollected waste from households, markets, construction sites, institutions, and agricultural activities are indiscriminately dumped along roadsides, open spaces, water channels, and within residential neighborhoods. Such practices have led to environmental degradation and expose residents to various health hazards, including outbreaks of communicable diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and dysentery.

The absence of an efficient waste sorting and recycling system further compounds the problem, making sustainable waste management difficult to achieve. Inconsistent waste collection, lack of appropriate facilities, inadequate manpower, and limited financial resources has resulted in indiscriminate dumping, overflowing waste bins, and blocked drainage systems (Henry, Yongsheng, & Jun, 2006). These challenges have intensified public concern and highlight the urgent need for effective intervention from local authorities. Therefore, there is an imperative need to develop a more efficient

and sustainable solid waste management system in Akoko South West, and by extension, Ondo State and Nigeria as a whole. Emphasizing the principles of waste reduction, reuse, and recycling would not only improve environmental cleanliness but also minimize pollution, promote public health, and ensure a safer, healthier, and more sustainable living environment for the populace.

This study considered socio-economic characteristics of the residents of the study area, and existing methods of waste disposal in order to investigate the connections between reduce, reuse and recycle of waste and their implications on waste management that would ensure sustainability of the environment. Therefore, this study seeks to appraised the nature of waste generated and method of waste disposal adopted in the study area with a view of providing community-based sustainable approach to solid waste management.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Sustainable waste management is understood as supervised handling of waste materials from source through recovery processes to disposal of it. It involves the control of generation, storage, collection, transportation, processing and disposal of solid waste with the aim of protecting environmental quality, human health and preservation of natural resources (Ojo, & Bowen, 2014). Used as conservation approach, the emphasis is laid on reduction, reusing and recycling of biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste (Ogunrinola & Omosalewa, 2012) and providing an environmentally friendly option to manage waste (Crown, 2012). The first R (reduce) involves prevention and reduction of waste. To reduce waste means to minimize amounts of waste generated. Waste reduction stresses upon judicious use of resources in manufacturing. The second R (reuse) involves

secondary and subsequent uses of waste materials either in part or as a whole. Reuse of waste is exemplified by trade in second-hand goods, such as: - cloths, electronics, automobiles, furniture and other merchandise (Goldman & Ogishi, 2001).

The “3Rs” is aimed at achieving sustainable solid waste management and also relates to other global environmental challenges. These challenges include climate change mitigation and specifically, the emission of greenhouse gases that could create sustainable development co-benefits and reduction in the emissions of methane (CH₄), biogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen oxide (NO_x) and carbon monoxide (CO) from landfills (Dlamini, Rampedi, & Ifegbesan, 2017).

There are many methods for solid waste management in urban areas, the most common being; incineration, dumping, re-use, and recycling. Best options such as re-use and recycling are highly recommended, although they are usually expensive and difficult to undertake where the wastes are not sorted. Often waste recycling is one of the techniques employed by the urban poor through the re-use of refuse. It is undertaken as a survival strategy when the urban poor are unable to obtain formal employment and when non-waste resources are unaffordable.

According to Cunningham and Saigo (2001), open dumping is still the predominant method of waste disposal in most developing countries. The giant mega cities have enormous garbage problems. For example, Mexico City which is the largest city in the world, which generates 10,000 tons of garbage each day, most of it is left in giant piles posing hazards to human and environment. In Manila Philippines, huge open dumps are common some of them reaching 30 meters high and home to thousands of people who derive their

survival from waste. Although most developed nations forbid open dumping, illegal dumping is still found there.

In the Multan City of Pakistan, some of the refuse generated from households and commercial areas partly is indiscriminately thrown on the roadsides. Occasionally, makeshift types of containers are used for storage of wastes at the premises mainly in the inner part of the city. Communal waste storage is made in different ways based on the nature of the area. There are 26 non sanitary deposits in the city to collect waste and act as transfer stations to load the waste for final disposal.

In East African countries solid waste management is also increasingly becoming a big problem. The study on pen-urban settlement in Uganda, Nuwagaba, (1995), observed that 40% of the households dispose solid waste in open space, 35% into drainage channel, and it is only 25% which get disposed of in refuse collection bins. However, in Kampala city, sanitary landfill in Kitezi was recently constructed for the final disposal of municipal solid waste (NEMA 2004). In Tanzania management of solid waste like other African countries, is still at low level especially in big urban centers Arusha inclusive. According to Thomas (2003), only

8.1% of the wastes generated (1,770 tons) in Dares Salaam is disposed of in the official final disposal site a crude open dump. In Arusha Municipality only 40% of 359 tons collected per day, are collected and disposed in open dump. The remaining 60% is not collected due to limited financial resources and other equipment (Arusha Municipal council, 2007).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

STUDY AREA

The study area is the Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo State Akoko. It is one of the four Local Government Area that made up Akoko region in the Northern Senatorial District of Ondo with the headquarter in Oka-Akoko. Akoko South West Local Government Area is located between latitude $5^{\circ} 31^1$ and $6^{\circ} 01$ North of the equator and between longitude $7^{\circ} 21^1$ and $7^{\circ} 31^1$ East of the Greenwich Meridian (Ale, 2016). Akoko SWLGA is bounded in the West by Emure LGA of Ekiti State and in the East by Akoko south east local government area of Ondo State while Akoko North East Local government Area and Owo Local Government Area of Ondo State bounded the study area in North and South respectively (see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Map of Ondo State Showing Akoko South West Local Government Area
 Source: Ministry of Land and Housing, Akure, 2022

Figure 2: Map of Akoko South West local government area Showing towns
 Source: Ministry of Land and Housing, Akure, 2022

Akoko South West Local Government Area is characterized by two seasons; the rainy and dry Season (Olagunju, 2022). The first and the second peak of rain come up between April to

July and August to October respectively. The two peak period are marked by annual rainfall of 1500-2000mm. He further claimed that the beginning of rainy season is marked by great

heat and storm that come along with lightning and thunder. Sometimes house and crops are destroyed according to Olagunju (2022) the annual temperature is between 23 – 26°C.

According to Ale (2014), the soil in the study area varies according to the bedrock and edaphic condition in general, some are metamorphic content. Although, the area is on the basement complex, the soil supporting the forests as result to the weathering of the basement rocks. The area under study is situated in the deciduous rainforest in south western part of Nigeria. This vegetation type reflects the rainforest and guinea savannah vegetation which is characterized by different plants and trees which varies in height. Intensive habitation, deforestation and cultivation modified the vegetation pattern of the study area.

Akoko South West Local Government Area is generally located within the western upland of South Western Nigeria. The topography is between 400 – 500 meter above the sea level (Ale 2006). Geologically, the study area is underlain by rock of the basement complex of South-Western Nigeria. The predominant rocks are granite-gneiss and grey gneiss, fault and fracture are also present in the rocks.

The entire population of the study area is 228,383 (National population census 2006). Out of this population 41.8% fall within the age 1-18 years old, 54.6% fall within 19-59 year while the remaining 3.6% are elderly age of 60 years

old and above. In 2012, estimated population increase to over 250,000 while the projected population for year 2020 is 372,182 and that 2024 is projected as 402,229 by annual population changes of 2.7%. The well in many parts of the study are shallow, reflecting the extent of the weathers profile in the study area. The economic activities of the study area can be grouped into primary, secondary and tertiary activities. The inhabitants engage predominantly in primary activities such as farming, oil palm production, cassava processing, and micro trading among others. Also, some engage in secondary activities like furniture making, welding and iron works, bakery, sachet water production among others, while the tertiary activities in the study area include banking, education and health services (Ale, 2014).

METHOD

The research adopted descriptive survey method. Data collected were through primary and secondary sources from the study area. Targeted populations were the household head of each sampled residential building, private and government -owned waste management staff and people around the sorting and dumping sites. Previous study by Ondo State Bureau for Statistics ODSB (2001) established that average household size in Nigeria is seven 7 as applied on the 3 selected wards in the table below:

Table 1: Projected population and sampled size of Akungba I, Akungba II and Ikun Akoko

Name of Ward	Based Population 2006	Projected Population	Household head population 7	10% of the Sample population	Sample Size of Household Per Building
Akungba I & Akungba II	15,579	26,071	3724	372	372
Ikun	4870	5,788	826	83	83
TOTAL	20407	31,859	4,550	455	455

Source: NPC 2006 and Authors projection 2024

The adoption of 10% of sample population as the sample size is (adjudged) in line with the recommendation of 4 - 6% sample for town within 300,000 to 1000,000 people by Pignatoro (1973) and Ogunbodede (1999). Using Taro Yamane formular as stated below, a sample of 395 satisfy the minimum population sample for this study. Adopting a higher figure as reflected from 10% permissible and had been adopted in this study for larger coverage. Structured questionnaires were used to collect relevant information for this study. Having stratified the study area into fifteen (15) wards in line with INEC 2024, three wards were purposively selected for this study.

Systemic Random Sampling technique was adopted to administer 455 copies of questionnaires on the 3 selected wards. The questionnaires were administered on the household head per building in the sample area at the interval of 10th occupied residential building. Scavengers, private and government-owned waste management staff e.g. AAUA, and people living around waste sorting and dumping sites were also slated for interview.

The data collected were analysed by descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive analysis employed the use of pie

chart, bar chart, and percentage count while inferential analysis adopted the application of analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the significant difference between the type of waste generated in different part of the wards and also between the method of wastes disposal system adopted. ANOVA was used to test whether the difference between the response of the selected wards were statistically significant. Also, four Likert scale was adopted in measuring the notion of respondent as it relates to environmental implications of reduce, reuse, and recycle of wastes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

a. Gender distribution of the Respondents

Table 1 show the gender distribution of the respondents. It was recorded that 64.8 % of respondents were male and 35.2% were female. This further explained 29.6% difference from the response received from the male. The reason for this result is not far-fetched, the observed scenario established the facts that male are the major subjects who are highly more involved in both in trading activities and physical activities.

Table 1: Showing the Gender Distribution of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	295	64.8
Female	174	35.2
Total	455	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

b. Educational Background of the Respondents

As depicted in Figure 3, it was observed that 3.1% of the respondents had elementary or primary school form of education, 20.7% had

secondary school form of education, and majority 76.2 % (majority) had access to other high forms of education. This implies that the majority of the respondents had formal education. It shows that the

respondents can write, read and understand issues on solid waste management, composition, human health and environmental

implications. The educational situation as observed in this study has assisted in accurate and knowledge-based response to questionnaire.

Figure 3: Educational Background of the Respondents
Source: Field Survey, 2025

c. Marital Status of the Respondents

The study revealed that 98.9% of the respondents were married and very few 1.1%

were single. This implies that most of respondents are responsible family men and women (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Marital Status of the Respondents
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

d. Monthly income of the Respondents

It was observed in the study that 6.8% of the respondents earn less than ₦15,000 monthly, 2.6% of the respondents earn between ₦16,000 and ₦40,000 per month, 22.6% of the respondents earn between ₦41,000-60,000, 31.9% earn between ₦61,000 and ₦80,000 per month, 4.6% earn between

₦81,000 and ₦100,000 per month while 31.4% of the respondents earn above ₦101,000 on monthly basis (Table 2). This finding shows that the respondents in the study area are more of moderately income earners with 143 flamboyant income earners. With this, one can say that the study area is still a growing sub-urban center.

Table 2: Monthly income of the respondents

Monthly income	Frequency	Percentage
< ₦15000	31	6.8
₦16000-40,000	12	2.6
₦41,000-60,000	103	22.6
₦61,000-80,000	145	31.9
₦81,000-100,000	21	4.6
above ₦101000	143	31.4
Total	455	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

VARIATION IN WASTE GENERATED IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 3 shows the computation of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of difference between the wastes generated in different part of Akoko South West, the f- statistics test computed showed a figure of $F(2, 454) = 58.84, P = 0.00 < 0.05$. Hence, null hypothesis that stated there is no significant difference between the

wastes generated in different part of Akoko South West were rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This implies there is significant difference between the wastes generated in different parts of Akoko South West at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the above statement shows there is a statistically significant difference in means of the wastes generated in different parts of Akoko South West [$F(2, 454) = 58.84, p = 0.00$].

Table 3: ANOVA showing difference between the wastes generated in different part of Akoko South West

Solid Waste		N	Mean (X)	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Ward 9	83	1.542				58.84	0.00
Between Groups	Ward 12	174	2.517	123.69	2	61.84		
Within Groups	Ward 13	198	2.995	475.05	452	1.051		
Total		455		598.73	454			

Computed using alpha = .05

Source: Field Survey (2025)

ASSESSMENT OF WASTE DISPOSAL METHODS IN THE STUDY AREA

The results on the assessment of waste disposal methods in the study area are depicted in Table 6. Item 1 on the table shows that a total of 83.5% of the respondents with the mean response (MWV = 3.19 > GMWV=3.13) said that they regularly participate in monthly environmental sanitation exercises in their wards, while 16.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. Hence, regular participation in monthly environmental sanitation exercises was accepted. Item 2 unveiled that the 77.2% (majority) with the mean response of the respondents (MWV = 3.21 > GMWV=3.13) do not use dustbin/trash-bag to collect their waste while 22.8% (minority) of the respondents disagreed. Item 3 shows that 50.8% of the respondents with the mean response (MWV = 1.57 < GMWV=3.13) were regularly visited by waste management team while 82.2% (majority) of the respondents disagree. Hence, regular visitation by sanitation team was rejected. Item 4 indicates that 84.6% (majority) with the mean responses (MWV 3.54 > GMWV = 3.13) said that government is not doing enough in the management of waste while 15.4% of the respondents disagreed. Item 5 also shows that 95.4% with the mean responses (MWV 3.58 > GMWV =3.13) agreed that waste disposal

method is a problem in the neighborhood while 4.6% of the respondents disagreed. Item 6 shows that 96% (majority) with the mean response of the respondents (MWV 3.69 > GMWV =3.13) agreed that improper waste management constitute public health problem while 4.6% of the respondents disagreed, hence, it is accepted that improper waste management constitute health problem.

The study observed, irregular services rendered to producers of waste by environmental sanitation authority or municipal councils compel them to find ways of disposing of refuse. A larger percentage of the population do not use dustbin/trash bag to collect their waste, hence dump their refuse in unauthorized sites in their neighborhood, if this trend is not addressed, it may become a breeding space for mosquitoes and other disease vectors.

This finding also agreed with Olabode, (2018) who reported that the residents of Akungba Akoko lack this basic waste container in their various homes, which is responsible for improper disposal of waste in the area. Also, Benneh, et al. (1993) established that the capacity to handle all the household waste generally is weak and larger percentage of the population dump refuse in either authorized or unauthorized sites in their neighborhood which creates adverse environmental issues.

Table 4: Assessment of Waste Disposal Methods.

S/N	ITEMS		SA	A	D	SD	MWV	DECISION
1	I regularly participate in monthly environmental sanitation exercises in this ward	F	164	216	75	-	3.19	Accept
		%	36.0	47.5	16.5	-		
2	I used dustbin/trash bag to collect my waste	F	276	75	104	-	3.21	Accept
		%	60.7	16.5	22.8	-		
3	Waste management team regularly visit on community to collect waste	F	31	50	68	306	1.57	Reject
		%	6.8	11.0	14.9	67.3		
4	Government is not doing enough in the management of waste	F	338	47	49	21	3.54	Accept
		%	74.3	10.3	10.8	4.6		
5	Waste disposal method is a problem in the neighbourhood	F	286	148	21	-	3.58	Accept
		%	62.9	32.5	4.6	-		
6	Improper waste management constitute public health problem.	F	334	103	18	-	3.69	Accept
		%	73.4	22.6	4.0	-		
GMWV							3.13	

VARIATION IN METHODS OF WASTE DISPOSAL SYSTEM IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 5 show the result of the computation of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of difference between the methods of waste disposal system adopted in different wards in Akoko South West, the f- statistics test computed showed a figure of $F(2, 454) = 4.520, P = 0.01 < 0.05$. Hence, null hypothesis that stated there is no significant difference between the methods of

waste disposal system adopted in different wards in Akoko South West was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This implies there is significant difference between the methods of waste disposal system adopted in different wards in Akoko South West at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a statistically significant difference in the means of the wastes generated in different part of Akoko South West in relation to methods of waste disposal system adopted [$F(2, 454) = 4.520, p = 0.01$].

Table 5: ANOVA Analysis showing difference between the methods of waste disposal system adopted in different wards in Akoko South West

Solid Waste	N	Mean (X)	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Ward 9	83	1.00				4.520	0.01
Between Groups	Ward 12	174	1.31	5.851	2		
Within Groups	Ward 13	198	1.27	292.51	452	0.647	
Total	455		598.73	454			

Computed using alpha = .05
 Source: Field Survey (2025)

TYPES AND VARIATION OF SOLID WASTE IN THE STUDY AREA

TYPES OF SOLID WASTES

Table 6 delineates the constituents of solid waste in Akoko South-West, Ondo State, according to survey responses. Of the total population, 23.5% cited paper and carton as salient components, 28.1% recorded the prevalence of plastic bags and bottles, 18.5% highlighted organic waste, and a plurality of 29.9% identified tin and can as the predominant waste type. Analysis suggests that paper, carton, and tin/can account for the largest portion of solid waste, a pattern likely influenced by the demographic composition of the sample. Approximately two-fifths of the respondents were drawn from wards 12 and 13, which are predominantly student communities, and their diets are heavily

reliant on fast-food items that are packaged in paper, carton, and tin. These observations corroborate the findings of Ilemobade and Olarewaju (2009), who reported analogous results for Akure South and the Ondo North senatorial district. Their assessment characterized the waste stream as comprising domestic and commercial fractions, with organic matter, plastics, tin/can, paper, and carton emerging as the major components, and less than 1% of the total as metal waste.

The phenomenon can be attributed to the acute demand for sachet water in Akoko South West, a region where the scarcity of potable water has become chronic. Concurrently, the proliferation of single-use packaging materials—including, but not limited to, Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles and sachet bags—has further exacerbated the environmental burden.

Table 6: Types and Classification of Solid Wastes

Types and classification of waste	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Paper and carton	107	23.5
Plastic bag/bottle	128	28.1
Food waste	84	18.5
Tin/can	136	29.9

Source: Field Survey (2025)

METHODS OF WASTE DISPOSAL IN THE STUDY AREA

TYPES OF WASTE DISPOSAL METHODS

Table 7 quantifies the modes of waste disposal employed by citizens within the investigative locality. Within Akoko South West Local Government Area, four predominant waste-management strategies were systematically recorded. Burning of waste accounted for 70.1% of the responses, while 18% admitted to discarding refuse into open drainages

during precipitation periods. Waste burial, employed by 9% of the cohort, and formal disposal at designated collection sites by just 2.9% complete the empirical picture. Major outcomes point toward widespread acceptance of waste incineration, a posture this dataset corroborates. This study is in firm agreement with the work of Olabode (2018) who reported that the residents of Akungba-Akoko lack basic waste containers in their various homes which is responsible for improper disposal of wastes in the area.

Table 7: Methods of Waste Disposal in the Study Area

Types of waste disposal methods	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Burning	319	70.1
Dumping wastes into open drainage during rainfall	82	18
Burying	41	9
Dumping at waste collection point	13	2.9

Source: Field Survey (2025).

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that majority of the wastes generated by the residents of Akoko South West LGA are municipal wastes like paper and carton, plastic bag/bottle, tin/can and food waste. This study also concluded that open burning, dumping of

wastes into the open drainage and burying of wastes were predominant among the residents due to inadequate and irregular service of the waste management team. Therefore, the study recommended an integrated waste management methods of waste disposal especially recycling for sustainable waste management in the study area.

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